

INVESTIGATION OF TEXTILE DEFORMATION IN LIQUID COMPOSITE MOLDING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Liquid composite molding (LCM) is one of the promising solutions for high-speed mass production of composite parts for automotive applications. In high pressure resin transfer molding (HPRTM) process which is the most popular LCM process in recent automotive industry, textile preform deforms undesirably by the high pressure resin flow, which causes defectives in size, properties and appearance of the final composite products. Therefore, process condition should be strictly controlled in order to prevent preform deformation in HPRTM. In this study, the deformations of fiber preform are classified by the pattern, which are slip, wrinkle, packing, etc. The competing forces on fiber preform in liquid molding process are measured to investigate the dominant factors on textile deformation. Coulomb and hydrodynamic friction coefficients are measured for obtaining the friction force in dry and wet states of fiber preform. A kind of bulk stiffness of fiber preform is measured to describe the resisting force of the preform itself. Deformation of fiber preform is investigated as flow front advances through the preform, and the corresponding fluid pressure is measured in HPRTM process. The process conditions preventing the fiber deformation in the molding process can be predicted by comparing the friction force, bulk stiffness of fiber preform and flow pressure. Several parameters regarding structure and process, which are fiber volume fraction, stacking structure of the constituent laminate and injection pressure, are investigated to determine the key factor and the important process criteria to prevent textile deformations.

1 INTRODUCTION

As international environment regulations for transportation equipment are strengthened, technology for improving fuel efficiency by applying lightweight parts has been actively developed. Carbon fiber reinforced composite is one of the most promising lightweight material with superior mechanical properties for the application to automotive industry. Automotive industry requires the mass production system of composite parts, for which cost reduction and fast speed of manufacturing process are inevitable. Besides many efforts for cost reduction of carbon fiber and matrix resin, development of optimum process for manufacturing composites has been promoted. High pressure resin transfer molding process has been applied to mass production of carbon fiber reinforced composite automotive parts in some of the companies [1].

Fiber preform can be deformed by flow induced force in the course of resin impregnation into the preform, which causes defects in appearance as well as mechanical properties. The deformation of fiber preform is probably influenced by structural factors such as fiber volume fraction, stacking structure, and friction coefficient, and process related factors such as injection pressure. Various types of deformation, slip, wrinkle, and shrinkage can be appeared [2,3].

In this study, various types of deformation in fiber preform were observed by both structural and process related parameters and relating forces were investigated to identify the mechanism of each deformation mode. It is expected that conditions for causing the deformation can be clarified, and optimum structural and process conditions without the undesired deformations can be designed.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Friction force is main force to resist flow induced preform deformation. To define friction forces during resin impregnation into the fiber preform, Coulomb friction coefficient was used in the unfilled region and hydrodynamic friction coefficient was used in the filled region as shown in Fig. 1. Hydrodynamic friction coefficient (μ) is defined by introducing Hersey number (H) as shown in equation 1, where η_R is viscosity of resin, U is moving velocity, and N is normal force onto the mold [4].

$$\mu = \mu(H), \quad H = \eta_R U / N \quad (1)$$

The resultant friction force at the specific time is estimated by applying rule of mixture on friction coefficients and the corresponding areas in the unfilled and filled regions. The friction force is mainly related with rigid body deformation of fiber preform by flow force of resin.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of relating forces during resin impregnation in liquid composite molding

Fiber preform is generally not a rigid body but an easily deformable material which depends on orientation pattern. For example, whereas unidirectional fabric aligned to parallel direction of force shows a rigid body like behaviour, that aligned to vertical direction of force deforms easily by only a small force. In this study, stiffness of fiber preform placed in the mold is defined as in-mold stiffness, which is closely related to local deformation of fiber preform. Three main kinds of forces acting on the resin impregnation process in liquid composite molding are schematically described in Fig. 1.

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Friction coefficient

Equipment for measuring Coulomb and hydrodynamic friction coefficients was prepared as shown in Fig. 2, which was composed by measuring frame for friction force, pneumatic cylinder for generating normal force, step motor controlling horizontal motion of fiber preform, etc [2]. Unidirectional carbon fabric from Zoltek (PANEX 35 50K UD150) was used for reinforcement and silicon oil from Shinetsu (KF-96H-10000CS) was used for matrix fluid. Friction coefficients at several Hersey numbers were investigated by combining several measurement conditions shown in table 1.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of equipment for measuring coulomb and hydrodynamic friction coefficients

Factor	Condition
Orientation angle (°)	0/45/90
Normal force (N)	100 / 300 / 500
Velocity (m/s)	0.0101 / 0.0202 / 0.0303
Viscosity (Pa·s)	0.341 / 0.975

Table 1: Test conditions for measurement of hydrodynamic friction coefficient

3.2 In-mold stiffness of fiber preform

Experimental setup for measuring in-mold stiffness of fiber preform was shown in Fig. 3, which was composed of mold system of same geometrical structure with liquid molding experiment and universal test machine (UTM) to apply strain and measure stress in the fiber preform. Test conditions are summarized in table 2.

Figure 3: Measurement system for in-mold stiffness of fiber preform

Factor	Condition	
Fiber	Orientation angle (°)	0/45/90
	Volume fraction (%)	40 / 50 / 55
Fluid	Viscosity (Pa.s)	0.341
	Flow rate (cm ³ /s)	0.838 / 2.513

Table 2: Test condition for measuring in-mold stiffness and flow induced deformation of fiber preform

3.3 Flow induced deformation of fiber preform in liquid composite molding

Measurement system for observing the flow induced deformation of fiber preform in liquid composite molding was equipped as shown in Fig. 4. It is based on unidirectional resin transfer molding equipment with constant flow rate condition, and has transparent mold side from top and lateral sides, which makes it possible to observe flow front advancement. Several test conditions on orientation angle, volume fraction of fiber preform and flow rate of fluid were applied, which is equivalent to measurement of in-mold stiffness as shown in table 2.

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of equipment for measuring flow induced deformation of fiber preform in liquid composite molding. (a) overall equipment, (b) inside of mold

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Friction coefficients measured from dry and wet states of fiber preform were represented with respect to orientation angle in table 3. Coulomb and hydrodynamic friction coefficients showed similar trend with respect to orientation angle of fiber preform, which has the largest value in orientation angle of 0° and decreased with increasing the orientation angle.

orientation angle	0°	45°	90°
dry	0.142	0.134	0.130
wet	0.092	0.089	0.076

Table 3: Friction coefficient with respect to orientation angle of fiber preform in dry and wet states

Images of flow induced deformation in orientation angles of 0° , 45° , 90° are shown in Fig. 5. Different types of deformation are observed with respect to orientation angle of fiber preform. In the direction of 0° , only a rigid body deformation which is shown as slip was observed. However, local deformations were clearly observed in the direction of 45° and 90° . This kind of different deformation behavior may be caused by different force balance between the related forces during resin impregnation process in liquid composite molding.

Figure 5: Deformation image of fiber preform in various orientation angles. (a) 0°, (b) 45°, (c) 90°

Three kinds of the related forces which are friction, in-mold stiffness and flow induced forces were compared to investigate factors that caused various deformations of fiber preform at specific conditions (orientation angle of 90° at flow rate of 0.838 and 2.513 cm³/s) in the Fig. 6. It is clearly verified that rigid body deformation is occurred when flow force is bigger than friction force regardless strength of in-mold stiffness induced force. On the other hand, local deformation is occurred when flow force is bigger than in-mold stiffness even though it is smaller than friction force. Total slip was observed after local deformation at the edge part of fiber preform in the orientation angle of 45° and 90°. It means that in-mold stiffness induced force is increasing with flow front advances, which causes the change of the related force balance on the fiber preform.

Figure 6: Comparison of the related forces: friction, flow and in-mold stiffness induced force. (a) local deformation (90°, 0.838 cm³/s), (b) rigid body deformation after local deformation (90°, 2.513 cm³/s)

5 CONCLUSIONS

Several types of fiber preform deformation in liquid molding of carbon fiber reinforced composites were observed and the related forces are measured in order to investigate the mechanism of the deformations. Force balance between friction between fabric and mold surfaces, in-mold stiffness of fiber preform, and flow induced pressure was a key factor in determining types of the fiber preform deformation in liquid composite molding process. Strength of in-mold stiffness induced force in comparison with flow induced force and friction determined whether local deformation was occurred or only rigid body deformation was occurred at a specified process condition. It is expected that understanding of the mechanism for causing deformation of fiber preform will make it possible to optimize the structural and process condition prohibiting the undesired deformation in liquid composite molding.

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